

ISic3626

I.Sicily inscription 3626

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

Treppiedi, catacomb A

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645699

Bibliography

- Orsi, P. 1934. Italia meridionale e insulare. *Atti del III Congresso internazionale di archeologia cristiana, Ravenna, 25-30 settembre 1932*. Rome. pp. 129-154. At 151-152 no.3 fig.22
- Orsi, P. 1942. Sicilia Bizantina. Tivoli. At 225-226 tav.17
- Ferrua, A 1943-1944. Sicilia Bizantina. *Epigraphica*. 5-6: 85-100. At 98-99

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. La catacomba A e le iscrizioni di Treppiedi. In Di Stefano, G. (eds.), *La necropoli di Treppiedi a Modica*. Palermo. pp. 52-58. At 55-56 no.5

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